

GOTHIC: Graph-Overclustered Transformer-based Hierarchical Integrated Clustering

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Abstract

Clustering becomes unreliable when cluster identity is defined by global connectivity, non-convex geometry, and locally varying density, where centroid-based objectives and purely local linkage heuristics can produce systematic splits, merges, or strong sensitivity to tuning. We present a hierarchical clustering framework that first over-partitions the data into compact micro-clusters, constructs a sparse graph that captures neighborhood structure at the micro level, and then learns an attention-based merge scorer that evaluates candidate merges under global context. The scorer combines complementary cues from centroid geometry, boundary interactions between neighboring micro-clusters, and density-aware statistics, enabling merge decisions that are both locally informed and globally consistent as the hierarchy is formed. This design avoids reliance on a single fixed density scale and improves robustness in regimes with near-touching structures and multi-scale cluster shapes, while still performing competitively on well-separated data. Across a broad set of synthetic and real benchmarks, the resulting approach achieves stronger agreement with ground-truth partitions than standard clustering baselines and exhibits improved stability across challenging geometries.

Keywords: Clustering, Hierarchical clustering, Graph-based learning, Attention models, Over-clustering, Density-aware features

1 Introduction

Clustering aims to partition unlabeled data into coherent groups and is routinely used to summarize datasets, discover latent structure, and provide pseudo-labels for downstream learning. It is also one of the most common building blocks in exploratory pipelines, where practitioners expect methods to behave predictably across different data geometries and scales. Classical approaches remain popular because they are simple and efficient: partitioning objectives such as k -means [47, 50] (often paired with careful initialization [4]) provide strong baselines, while agglomerative strategies offer a multi-resolution view through hierarchical merging [78]. Other families prioritize different assumptions, including density-based clustering [3, 11, 25, 49] and probabilistic mixture modeling optimized with EM [8, 21]. Graph and spectral formulations connect clustering to Laplacian geometry and graph partitioning [53, 64, 77]. Overviews of these directions highlight how different objectives trade off robustness, interpretability, and computational cost [40, 41, 81].

A recurring practical issue is that the "right" bias depends strongly on the dataset. Methods that are computationally convenient can struggle when clusters are elongated, multi-modal, or separated by thin manifolds. Conversely, methods that better capture non-convex structure often rely on density or graph construction parameters that can be difficult to set reliably when density varies across regions or when distances concentrate in high dimensions. These challenges become more pronounced at scale: approaches that reason over all point-to-point relationships are expensive, while approximate pipelines introduce additional design choices (neighbor search, sparsification, affinity normalization) that can dominate results. In modern workloads—large sample counts, high-dimensional embeddings, and heterogeneous densities—this pushes many systems toward compact intermediate representations and sparse relational structures.

One effective strategy is to compress the dataset into small, locally coherent units and then reason at a higher level of abstraction. Large-scale clustering methods explicitly follow this philosophy by building summaries and merging them [62, 88]. When clustering is viewed through a graph lens, sparse neighborhood graphs provide a natural substrate for connecting these units, but they also raise a central question: given a limited set of candidate connections, how should we decide which links correspond to "same-cluster" relationships and which should be cut? Hand-crafted affinities based on distances or shared neighbors are often insufficient when local geometry is ambiguous, when there are bridges between clusters, or when the feature space is itself learned and changes across datasets.

At the same time, clustering is increasingly coupled with representation learning. Deep clustering and self-supervised learning have shown that the embedding space can be shaped so that simple grouping rules become effective [12, 13, 16, 38, 42, 72, 79]. Attention mechanisms provide an additional ingredient: they model interactions in a data-dependent way rather than relying on a fixed similarity function [73]. Transformers have become a strong default for learning such interaction patterns in vision [24] and are closely related to graph attention and message passing when applied to relational data [45, 74]. This motivates a clustering design where the core decision is

Fig. 1: GOTHIC overview. The dataset is first over-partitioned into compact micro-clusters using k -means. A sparse graph is built over micro-clusters. Node feature vectors are projected and encoded with a Transformer to produce contextual node embeddings. For each candidate edge, the incident node embeddings are concatenated with edge features and scored by an FFN to predict a merge probability $\rho_{i,j}$. Micro-clusters are then merged greedily with Union-Find until the target number of clusters is reached.

not a global objective solved in one shot, but a learned policy that predicts which local regions of the space should be merged.

In this work, we propose **GOTHIC** (Graph-Overclustered Transformer-based Hierarchical Integrated Clustering), a graph-based hierarchical clustering framework that turns sample-level clustering into a *micro-cluster merging* problem. The pipeline is summarized in Fig. 1. GOTHIC first deliberately over-clusters the dataset into many small, tight micro-clusters using k -means [47, 50]. It then constructs a sparse micro-cluster graph that restricts candidate merges to a tractable neighborhood. To learn merge decisions, we encode micro-cluster node features with a Transformer encoder [73], producing contextual node embeddings that reflect interactions among nearby micro-clusters. For each graph edge (i, j) , we concatenate the learned embeddings of nodes i and j with edge-level features and apply a feed-forward network to output a merge probability. Finally, we apply greedy merging using a Union-Find structure [69] until the desired number of clusters is obtained. This design preserves the efficiency benefits of operating on a compact micro-level representation [62, 88] while replacing fixed affinity rules with learned, interaction-aware merge scoring.

Our main contributions are:

- **Micro-cluster graph formulation for hierarchical clustering:** we recast clustering as iterative merging over an over-partitioned set of micro-clusters connected by a sparse graph, reducing the search space compared to point-wise merging.
- **Transformer-based merge scoring aligned with the graph structure:** we obtain contextual node embeddings with self-attention [73] and score candidate merges by combining incident node embeddings with edge features through an FFN, producing merge probabilities.
- **Efficient greedy merging with explicit target control:** we use a Union-Find-based procedure [69] to merge micro-clusters efficiently while directly controlling the final number of clusters.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 places our approach in the context of prior work. Section 3 details the proposed GOTHIC framework. Section 4 presents the experimental setup and empirical results, including comparisons to established baselines. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the main findings and outlines limitations and future directions.

2 Related Work

Clustering spans a broad set of perspectives, from classical objectives and scalable pre-processing to graph-based formulations and learned representations. The discussion below focuses on directions most closely connected to GOTHIC: micro-level summarization, sparse graph reasoning, attention-based embedding, and edge-level decisions that support hierarchical merging.

Classical clustering, scalability, and neighborhood graphs: Partition-based clustering remains a strong baseline because it is efficient and directly controls the number of clusters [4, 47, 50]. Hierarchical agglomeration provides a multi-resolution view, though its behavior depends on linkage design and maintaining pairwise relations can be costly; efficient formulations and implementations address part of this burden [51, 65, 78]. Other classical families emphasize different structure assumptions, including density-based discovery of non-convex clusters and robustness to outliers [3, 11, 25, 49], and probabilistic mixtures optimized with EM [8, 21]. At scale, many systems reduce computation by compressing the dataset into compact representatives before global decisions, as in summary-based clustering pipelines [30, 33, 34, 62, 88]. Graph-based pipelines also depend on efficient sparse neighborhood construction; approximate k NN graph building and ANN indices enable scalable similarity search and graph formation in high-dimensional spaces [23, 43, 48]. This compression-and-sparsification view aligns with GOTHIC, where micro-clusters replace raw samples and candidate merges are restricted to sparse graph edges.

Graph partitioning, spectral clustering, and community detection: When data are represented as graphs, clustering connects naturally to graph partitioning and Laplacian geometry. Normalized-cut objectives and spectral relaxations yield partitions that respect graph connectivity when affinities are well constructed [53, 64, 77].

Laplacian-based embeddings preserve local neighborhood structure and support clustering in a low-dimensional space [7], while locally adaptive affinities aim to stabilize similarity construction across varying densities [87]. In network science, community detection targets connectivity-driven groups, with widely used methods based on modularity optimization and refinement [9, 52, 70], information-flow criteria [58], and lightweight propagation dynamics [55]. Learning-based community methods increasingly incorporate node attributes and graph encoders to optimize objectives correlated with partition quality [20, 60, 71]. These lines motivate GOTHIC’s reliance on a sparse relational substrate, while differing in how decisions are made: GOTHIC learns merge probabilities on a micro-cluster graph and performs hierarchical merging rather than solving a single partitioning objective.

Representation learning for clustering and self-supervision: Deep clustering couples feature learning with iterative assignment refinement to reduce dependence on hand-crafted similarity rules [36, 79, 82]. Other approaches use clustering itself to generate pseudo-label supervision, iterating between grouping and representation updates to strengthen semantic structure [12, 42, 72]. Self-supervised learning has further advanced this embedding-first view by producing feature spaces that often exhibit strong emergent grouping behavior [6, 13, 14, 16, 17, 31, 38]. Recent work in 2025 revisits deep clustering pipelines and emphasizes self-supervision as a primary driver of cluster formation, reducing reliance on brittle pseudo-label schedules while improving stability [18, 63]. GOTHIC is complementary: it can operate on embeddings learned by these methods, but focuses on a different stage by learning how to merge micro-clusters under sparse graph constraints.

Graph representation learning, attention, and edge-level prediction: Unsupervised and self-supervised graph representation learning provides embeddings that support downstream grouping and prediction. Random-walk embeddings capture neighborhood co-occurrence patterns that are effective for node classification and can be clustered to recover communities [32, 54, 68]. Relatedly, HyEMST combines distance and density information through a hybrid affinity over an over-segmented representation and uses a maximum spanning tree to support density-aware merging, providing a complementary MST-based route to robust clustering under arbitrary shapes and heterogeneous densities [26]. Autoencoder-style models learn latent node vectors by reconstructing edges, providing another route to unsupervised embeddings and link prediction [44]. Message-passing GNNs contextualize node features through iterative neighborhood aggregation [37, 45, 80], while attention-based variants learn data-dependent neighbor weighting [74]. Graph transformers extend self-attention to graphs using structural encodings and hybrid local-global designs [56, 84], and recent work consolidates architectural choices and applications across domains [5, 66, 86]. These models are often used as general feature embedders: the encoder produces contextual node representations, and downstream modules perform edge classification or link prediction by scoring pairs of node embeddings. This aligns with GOTHIC’s merge predictor, where contextual node embeddings on the micro-cluster graph are combined with explicit edge features and passed through an FFN to estimate merge probabilities, followed by efficient greedy merging with Union-Find [69].

3 GOTHIC

We introduce **GOTHIC**, a graph-based hierarchical clustering framework that converts a standard sample-level clustering problem into a *micro-cluster merging* problem. The core idea is to (i) over-partition the training data into many compact micro-clusters, (ii) build a sparse graph over these micro-clusters, (iii) learn a *pairwise merge score* on graph edges with a Transformer encoder [73], and (iv) greedily merge micro-clusters (via Union-Find) until reaching a desired number of clusters. This design aims to combine the stability and efficiency of clustering at the micro level with the representational power of attention-based models for deciding which regions of the space should be merged.

Let the dataset be

$$\mathcal{D} = \{(\mathbf{x}_n, y_n)\}_{n=1}^N, \quad \mathbf{x}_n \in \mathbb{R}^d. \quad (1)$$

In our implementation, labels are used only to construct training-time pairwise merge targets on the *training split* (no test labels are used by the model). We form \mathcal{D}_{tr} and \mathcal{D}_{te} using either a standard random split or an optional density-balanced split. The main motivation behind the density-balanced split is the following: in many clustering datasets, a random split disproportionately assigns *high-density interior* points to the training set. These interior points are typically "easy" in the sense that their local neighborhood structure is consistent and the correct merge decisions are rarely ambiguous. In contrast, the merge mistakes that dominate hierarchical clustering errors usually occur near *cluster boundaries*, along low-density transition regions (e.g., bridges), or where two clusters approach each other closely. If training is dominated by interior points, a learned merge scorer can achieve high training accuracy while still failing to learn boundary-sensitive behavior, resulting in poor generalization precisely on the difficult cases.

To reduce this mismatch, the density-balanced split deliberately assigns a larger portion of dense interior points to \mathcal{D}_{te} and retains a comparatively larger portion of boundary/ambiguous points in \mathcal{D}_{tr} . This design makes the supervised signal used to train the merge scorer more representative of the decisions that determine final clustering quality, while still preserving class proportions in both splits. Concretely, for each point \mathbf{x}_i we define a local density proxy based on within-class k -nearest neighbors:

$$\hat{\rho}(\mathbf{x}_i) = \frac{1}{\varepsilon + \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\pi_j(i)}\|_2}, \quad (2)$$

where $\pi_j(i)$ denotes the index of the j -th nearest neighbor of \mathbf{x}_i among points of the same class, and $\varepsilon > 0$ is a small constant. This proxy follows a standard geometric intuition: dense interior points have small average neighbor distance and therefore larger $\hat{\rho}$, while boundary points, sparse regions, and local outliers have larger neighbor distances and therefore smaller $\hat{\rho}$. The constant ε is included for numerical stability and to avoid division-by-zero in the presence of duplicates or extremely small neighbor distances. In practice we also cap k by the class size, i.e., $k = \min(k_{\text{max}}, n_c - 1)$,

ensuring the density estimate remains well-defined even for small classes and remains *local* rather than becoming a global statistic.

Within each class, we sort points in descending order of $\hat{\rho}$ and assign the densest fraction to \mathcal{D}_{te} , placing the remainder in \mathcal{D}_{tr} . Importantly, this is done *class-wise*, so the split maintains per-class proportions while changing which points are considered "train" versus "test". As a result, the training split is intentionally enriched with boundary and low-density cases, which are precisely the configurations where merge decisions are most informative.

Beyond the clustering motivation, this choice also addresses a practical learning concern that arises when using Transformer encoders for merge scoring. Transformers typically benefit from pretraining or large-scale supervision, whereas clustering benchmarks can be small, making direct end-to-end training on raw samples prone to overfitting and poor generalization. Our overall design mitigates this issue by training on micro-clusters rather than individual points, which compresses the dataset into representative regions and yields a structured set of pairwise training instances defined on graph edges. The density-balanced split further strengthens this by ensuring that these training instances are not dominated by trivial interior relationships. In effect, we attempt to make the available supervision *as informative as possible* under limited data: we keep the training distribution focused on hard, boundary-driven merge cases while still remaining faithful to the dataset geometry and preserving class balance.

Finally, we emphasize that the density-balanced split is optional and does not alter inference. At test time, the model operates without access to test labels, and all reported clustering metrics are computed on \mathcal{D}_{te} in the standard manner. In our experiments, enabling the density-balanced split often improves robustness when a random split yields an overly optimistic training signal and under-exposes the model to the boundary-driven failure modes that determine final clustering performance.

3.1 Over-clustering into micro-clusters

GOTHIC starts by applying K -means [47, 50] on the training data to create an over-partition into K micro-clusters $\{\mathcal{C}_m\}_{m=1}^K$:

$$\min_{\{\boldsymbol{\mu}_m\}_{m=1}^K} \sum_{m=1}^K \sum_{\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{C}_m} \|\mathbf{x}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_m\|_2^2, \quad (3)$$

with centroids

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_m = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{C}_m|} \sum_{\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{C}_m} \mathbf{x}_i. \quad (4)$$

Over-clustering (choosing K larger than the final target number of clusters) transforms the problem into learning how to merge small, relatively homogeneous regions. This is particularly useful on synthetic 2D datasets where the global cluster geometry can be non-convex while local regions remain compact.

For each micro-cluster \mathcal{C}_m , we compute compact geometric descriptors that summarize its *scale* and *dispersion*. These descriptors serve two purposes: (i) they enrich

the node representation in the micro-graph beyond the centroid alone, and (ii) they provide coarse density/compactness cues that help distinguish whether two nearby micro-clusters plausibly belong to the same macro-cluster. We define the *radius* of a point $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{C}_m$ as its Euclidean distance to the micro-centroid $\boldsymbol{\mu}_m$:

$$r_{m,i} = \|\mathbf{x}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_m\|_2, \quad \bar{r}_m = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{C}_m|} \sum_{\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{C}_m} r_{m,i}, \quad \sigma_{r,m} = \text{Std}(\{r_{m,i}\}). \quad (5)$$

Here, \bar{r}_m is a characteristic micro-cluster scale (average distance-to-center), while $\sigma_{r,m}$ measures how heterogeneous the distances are, which can indicate non-sphericity, elongated shapes, or the presence of boundary points.

Using \bar{r}_m as a simple length-scale proxy, we further construct a coarse density estimate by approximating the micro-cluster "occupied volume" as proportional to $(\bar{r}_m)^d$ in d dimensions. This yields the density proxy

$$\rho_m = \frac{|\mathcal{C}_m|}{(\bar{r}_m)^d + \varepsilon}, \quad \ell_m = \log(1 + \rho_m), \quad (6)$$

where $\varepsilon > 0$ prevents numerical instability when \bar{r}_m is very small. The logarithm stabilizes the dynamic range of densities across micro-clusters of different sizes and scales, making the feature more suitable for learning.

We then represent each micro-cluster as a graph node with feature vector obtained by concatenating centroid coordinates with four scalar descriptors (log-size, mean radius, radius dispersion, and log-density):

$$\mathbf{f}_m = \left[\boldsymbol{\mu}_m; \log(1 + |\mathcal{C}_m|); \bar{r}_m; \sigma_{r,m}; \ell_m \right] \in \mathbb{R}^{d+4}. \quad (7)$$

A practical component of GOTHIC is the use of a small set of *boundary representatives* for each micro-cluster, computed exclusively from the training split. For a micro-cluster $\mathcal{C}_m \subset \mathcal{D}_{\text{tr}}$ with centroid $\boldsymbol{\mu}_m$, we rank its members by their radius $r_{m,i} = \|\mathbf{x}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_m\|_2$ and retain the b most distant points:

$$\mathcal{B}_m = \text{Top-}b\left(\{(\mathbf{x}_i, r_{m,i}) : \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{C}_m\}\right). \quad (8)$$

The set \mathcal{B}_m acts as a lightweight proxy for the micro-cluster boundary and is later used as an additional geometric cue when defining pairwise relations between micro-clusters (e.g., to complement centroid-based proximity). Since \mathcal{B}_m is extracted solely from \mathcal{D}_{tr} , it does not introduce any test-data leakage and keeps the entire graph construction and merge-learning pipeline strictly training-based.

3.2 Micro-cluster graph construction

We construct a sparse, undirected graph over micro-clusters by connecting only those pairs that are sufficiently close in centroid space. Let K_{eff} denote the number of

effective (non-empty) micro-clusters produced by the over-clustering step. For each pair of micro-clusters (i, j) , we define the centroid distance

$$D_{ij} = \|\boldsymbol{\mu}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_j\|_2. \quad (9)$$

Rather than selecting an absolute distance threshold (which is dataset-dependent), we choose a fraction parameter $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and compute a data-adaptive threshold τ from the empirical distribution of all pairwise centroid distances. Specifically, τ is set to the α -quantile of $\{D_{ij}\}_{i < j}$, meaning that approximately an α fraction of the distances are no larger than τ :

$$\tau = \text{Quantile}_\alpha(\{D_{ij} : 1 \leq i < j \leq K_{\text{eff}}\}), \quad \alpha \in (0, 1). \quad (10)$$

With this choice, α directly controls graph sparsity: smaller α produces a more local (sparser) graph, while larger α yields a denser graph. We then define the candidate edge set as

$$\mathcal{E} = \{(i, j) : 1 \leq i < j \leq K_{\text{eff}}, D_{ij} \leq \tau\}. \quad (11)$$

For each edge $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$, we also compute a boundary-based proximity term using the boundary representative sets \mathcal{B}_i and \mathcal{B}_j (extracted from the training split):

$$D_{ij}^{\text{bd}} = \min_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{B}_i, \mathbf{q} \in \mathcal{B}_j} \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q}\|_2. \quad (12)$$

While D_{ij} captures center-to-center proximity, D_{ij}^{bd} captures the closest interaction between the two micro-cluster outer shells, which is informative when centroid distances alone are ambiguous.

We form an edge feature vector by combining these geometric cues with density-compatibility signals derived from the log-density proxies ℓ_i and ℓ_j :

$$\mathbf{e}_{ij} = \left[D_{ij}, D_{ij}^{\text{bd}}, |\ell_i - \ell_j|, \ell_i, \ell_j \right] \in \mathbb{R}^5. \quad (13)$$

Here, ℓ_i (and similarly ℓ_j) is the *log-density* attribute of micro-cluster i , defined as $\ell_i = \log(1 + \rho_i)$ in 6. In \mathbf{e}_{ij} , the discrepancy $|\ell_i - \ell_j|$ provides a direct measure of density compatibility between two neighboring micro-clusters (large mismatches often indicate a boundary), while the absolute levels (ℓ_i, ℓ_j) let the model condition its merge decisions on the overall density regime, which can affect how reliable distance-based cues are.

Overall, the quantile-based rule yields a data-adaptive neighborhood graph controlled by α , and the resulting edge features combine centroid proximity, boundary proximity, and density compatibility to support robust micro-cluster relation modeling.

3.3 Transformer pair scorer

Given micro-cluster node descriptors $\{\mathbf{f}_m\}_{m=1}^{K_{\text{eff}}}$ (defined in 7), we learn a parametric *merge scorer* that outputs a probability p_{ij} for each candidate edge $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$. The probability p_{ij} is interpreted as the model confidence that micro-clusters i and j should be merged, meaning that they belong to the same underlying macro-cluster under the training-time supervision. Since each micro-cluster summarizes a local region of the dataset, the micro-clusters can be treated as a set of tokens, analogous to the patch tokens used in Vision Transformers [24]; here, the "patches" are formed by over-clustering in feature space rather than by partitioning an image grid.

We begin with a linear embedding layer that maps each node feature vector into a d_{model} -dimensional latent space:

$$\mathbb{R}^{K_{\text{eff}} \times d_{\text{model}}} \ni \mathbf{H}^{(0)} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{W}_{\text{in}} + \mathbf{1}\mathbf{b}_{\text{in}}^{\top}, \quad \mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_1^{\top} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{f}_{K_{\text{eff}}}^{\top} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{K_{\text{eff}} \times (d+4)}. \quad (14)$$

Here, $\mathbf{W}_{\text{in}} \in \mathbb{R}^{(d+4) \times d_{\text{model}}}$ and $\mathbf{b}_{\text{in}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}}}$ are learnable parameters.

We do not introduce a [CLS] token because the goal is not to produce a single global summary vector; instead, we require contextualized embeddings for all micro-clusters so that we can score multiple candidate merges.

Additionally, we do not include explicit positional embeddings. Our tokens correspond to micro-clusters, which form an unordered set rather than an ordered sequence or a spatial grid. Furthermore, geometric information is already carried by the micro-cluster descriptors (centroid coordinates and local scale statistics) and is complemented by edge-level features during pair scoring. Omitting positional embeddings avoids imposing an artificial ordering while retaining geometry through these explicit cues.

A Transformer encoder with L layers then produces contextualized node embeddings:

$$\mathbf{H} = \text{Enc}_{\theta}(\mathbf{H}^{(0)}) \in \mathbb{R}^{K_{\text{eff}} \times d_{\text{model}}}, \quad (15)$$

where θ denotes all learnable parameters of the encoder (attention projections, feed-forward weights, and normalization parameters). Each encoder layer follows the standard design of multi-head self-attention followed by a position-wise feed-forward network [73]. The superscript (t) in the attention equations denotes the head index $t \in \{1, \dots, h\}$, with h attention heads and per-head dimension $d_h = d_{\text{model}}/h$. For layer ℓ , queries, keys, and values are computed from $\mathbf{H}^{(\ell-1)} \in \mathbb{R}^{K_{\text{eff}} \times d_{\text{model}}}$ as

$$\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{H}^{(\ell-1)}\mathbf{W}_Q, \quad \mathbf{K} = \mathbf{H}^{(\ell-1)}\mathbf{W}_K, \quad \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{H}^{(\ell-1)}\mathbf{W}_V, \quad (16)$$

with $\mathbf{W}_Q, \mathbf{W}_K, \mathbf{W}_V \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}} \times d_{\text{model}}}$. For head t , we take the corresponding slices $\mathbf{Q}^{(t)}, \mathbf{K}^{(t)}, \mathbf{V}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{K_{\text{eff}} \times d_h}$ and compute

$$\mathbf{A}^{(t)} = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{\mathbf{Q}^{(t)} (\mathbf{K}^{(t)})^\top}{\sqrt{d_h}} \right) \in \mathbb{R}^{K_{\text{eff}} \times K_{\text{eff}}}, \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{O}^{(t)} = \mathbf{A}^{(t)} \mathbf{V}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{K_{\text{eff}} \times d_h}. \quad (18)$$

The matrix $\mathbf{A}^{(t)}$ is an attention (affinity) matrix: each row corresponds to a micro-cluster and distributes weight across all micro-clusters, determining how strongly its representation aggregates information from others. The h head outputs are concatenated and projected back to $\mathbb{R}^{K_{\text{eff}} \times d_{\text{model}}}$. A position-wise feed-forward network (FFN) is then applied; Meaning the same MLP is applied independently to each token vector (each row of \mathbf{H}), while cross-token interaction is handled by self-attention.

The FFN expands and contracts the token dimension using an MLP ratio r_{mlp} :

$$\text{FFN}(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{W}_2 \sigma(\mathbf{W}_1 \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{b}_1) + \mathbf{b}_2, \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}}}$, $\mathbf{W}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{(r_{\text{mlp}} d_{\text{model}}) \times d_{\text{model}}}$, and $\mathbf{W}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}} \times (r_{\text{mlp}} d_{\text{model}})}$.

After contextualization, we score a candidate edge $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$ by forming a pair representation that combines $(\mathbf{h}_i, \mathbf{h}_j)$ with edge features \mathbf{e}_{ij} (defined in 13). Specifically, we concatenate the two node embeddings together with their absolute difference and their Hadamard (element-wise) product:

$$\mathbf{z}_{ij} = \left[\mathbf{h}_i; \mathbf{h}_j; |\mathbf{h}_i - \mathbf{h}_j|; \mathbf{h}_i \odot \mathbf{h}_j; \mathbf{e}_{ij} \right] \in \mathbb{R}^{(4d_{\text{model}}+5)}. \quad (20)$$

The terms $|\mathbf{h}_i - \mathbf{h}_j|$ and $\mathbf{h}_i \odot \mathbf{h}_j$ provide complementary interaction cues that improve pair discrimination beyond raw concatenation.

The pair vector \mathbf{z}_{ij} is mapped to a scalar logit by a two-layer MLP with parameters ϕ :

$$s_{ij} = \text{MLP}_\phi(\mathbf{z}_{ij}), \quad p_{ij} = \sigma(s_{ij}) \in (0, 1), \quad (21)$$

where p_{ij} is interpreted as the merge probability for micro-clusters i and j under the training-time supervision. The parameters θ (encoder) and ϕ (pair MLP) are learned jointly using supervised targets defined over edges in \mathcal{E} , as described in the training subsection 3.4.

3.4 Training signal and objective

After over-clustering, we assign each micro-cluster a *majority label* based on the ground-truth labels of its member samples:

$$\tilde{y}_m = \text{mode}(\{y_i : \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{C}_m\}). \quad (22)$$

These majority labels are used only to define pairwise merge targets for training the merge scorer.

Using $\{\tilde{y}_m\}$, we define a binary target for each candidate edge $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$:

$$t_{ij} = \mathbb{I}[\tilde{y}_i = \tilde{y}_j], \quad (i, j) \in \mathcal{E}, \quad (23)$$

where $\mathbb{I}[\cdot]$ is the indicator function. The merge scorer outputs probabilities $p_{ij} \in (0, 1)$ as in 21, and we fit these probabilities to the targets by minimizing the average binary cross-entropy over edges:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta, \phi) = -\frac{1}{|\mathcal{E}|} \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{E}} \left(t_{ij} \log p_{ij} + (1 - t_{ij}) \log(1 - p_{ij}) \right). \quad (24)$$

The parameters are learned by minimizing 24 via backpropagation with a standard gradient-based optimizer. Although labels are used to construct t_{ij} , they are used only to train the merge scorer; the clustering produced at inference does not access labels.

3.5 Greedy hierarchical merging

After training, we compute merge probabilities $\{p_{ij}\}_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{E}}$ and form macro-clusters by greedily merging the most confident pairs. We maintain the evolving partition of micro-clusters using a Union-Find (disjoint-set union) structure [69], which tracks the current connected components as merges are applied.

We first sort all candidate edges in descending order of p_{ij} and process them in that order. Whenever an edge connects two different components and the current number of components is larger than the desired K_{target} , we merge the two components. This continues until the number of components equals K_{target} . After merging, each micro-cluster $m \in \{1, \dots, K_{\text{eff}}\}$ is assigned a macro-cluster identifier:

$$G_m \in \{1, \dots, K_{\text{target}}\}. \quad (25)$$

Similarly, the over-clustering step assigns each sample \mathbf{x}_n to a micro-cluster index

$$M_n \in \{1, \dots, K_{\text{eff}}\}. \quad (26)$$

The predicted cluster assignment for \mathbf{x}_n is obtained by mapping its micro-cluster to the corresponding macro-cluster:

$$\hat{y}_n = G_{M_n}. \quad (27)$$

If the learned merges are insufficient to reach K_{target} (for example, when the candidate graph is too sparse), we apply a deterministic distance-based fallback. Let \mathcal{S} denote the set of pairs (i, j) such that $1 \leq i < j \leq K_{\text{eff}}$ and i and j currently belong to different components. We then merge the closest such pair:

$$(i^*, j^*) = \arg \min_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{S}} D_{ij}. \quad (28)$$

Repeating this step until the number of components equals K_{target} guarantees termination with exactly K_{target} clusters.

3.6 Assigning cluster labels to points

Once micro-clusters have been merged into macro-clusters, each sample is assigned a macro-cluster ID through its associated micro-cluster. Let $G_m \in \{1, \dots, K_{\text{target}}\}$ denote the macro-cluster identifier of micro-cluster m after merging (as in 25). For a training sample \mathbf{x}_n , the over-clustering step provides its micro-cluster index $M_n \in \{1, \dots, K_{\text{eff}}\}$ (as in 26), and the predicted cluster assignment is

$$\hat{y}_n = G_{M_n}. \quad (29)$$

For a test sample \mathbf{x} , we assign it to the nearest effective micro-centroid and then use the corresponding macro label. Let $\boldsymbol{\mu}_m$ denote the centroid of micro-cluster m . We define

$$M^*(\mathbf{x}) = \arg \min_{1 \leq m \leq K_{\text{eff}}} \|\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_m\|_2, \quad (30)$$

and predict

$$\hat{y}(\mathbf{x}) = G_{M^*(\mathbf{x})}. \quad (31)$$

In the merge scorer, pairwise edge features \mathbf{e}_{ij} in 13 provide direct relational cues between candidate micro-cluster pairs, including density-related terms derived from ℓ_m in 6.

Viewed as a whole, GOTHIC learns a data-dependent linkage rule for hierarchical merging on top of an over-clustered graph representation. The micro-cluster abstraction yields a compact set of representative regions for learning, boundary-aware edge features complement centroid proximity, and the Transformer encoder supplies global context by allowing each micro-cluster embedding to depend on the full set of micro-clusters, which helps disambiguate merge decisions in crowded regions and non-convex geometries.

4 Experiments

This section describes the experimental protocol used to evaluate **GOTHIC** (Section 3). We report results on both synthetic clustering benchmarks and standard real datasets, using a fixed and reproducible training/testing split and a consistent set of external and internal evaluation metrics.

Execution environment and code availability All experiments were executed on a single workstation running Windows 11, equipped with a 13th Gen Intel Core i5-1335U CPU and 24 GB of RAM (8 GB + 16 GB). No discrete GPU was used; all runs were performed on the CPU. The full implementation, configuration files, and scripts for reproducing the experiments are publicly available at <https://github.com/amkharazi/GOTHIC>.

Dataset	Type	N	d	K
compound [29]	Synthetic	399	2	6
aggregation [29]	Synthetic	788	2	7
d31 [29]	Synthetic	3100	2	31
flame [29]	Synthetic	240	2	2
jain [29]	Synthetic	373	2	2
pathbased [15, 29]	Synthetic	300	2	3
r15 [29]	Synthetic	600	2	15
noisy_circles	Synthetic	1500	2	2
breast_cancer [67]	Real	569	30	2
iris [27, 83]	Real	150	4	3
wine [22]	Real	178	13	3
olivetti_faces [61]	Real	400	4096	40
digits [2]	Real	1797	64	10

Table 1: Datasets used in the experimental evaluation. N is the number of samples, d is the feature dimensionality, and K is the number of ground-truth clusters/classes. The synthetic benchmarks are sourced from the SIPU collection [29], while the real datasets follow their standard definitions [2, 22, 27, 61, 67, 83].

4.1 Datasets

We evaluate on 8 synthetic datasets and 5 real datasets. The synthetic benchmarks are drawn from the SIPU clustering dataset collection, which is widely used to assess geometric and non-convex cluster structure in low-dimensional settings [29]. These datasets provide diverse cluster geometries, including compact groups, elongated structures, varying inter-cluster separation, and cases with partial overlap, offering controlled scenarios for evaluating merge decisions in hierarchical procedures.

The real datasets include standard tabular benchmarks from the UCI repository with well-defined class semantics: Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) contains two classes corresponding to benign versus malignant tumors [67]; Iris contains three classes corresponding to three iris species [27, 83]; and Wine contains three classes corresponding to wines from three cultivars derived from the same region [22]. In addition, we include two higher-dimensional real benchmarks commonly used in clustering: Olivetti Faces (AT&T) consists of grayscale face images from 40 subjects [61] (we treat subject identity as the ground-truth partition), and Optical Digits contains 10 digit classes derived from 8×8 image features [2]. In all cases, the class labels serve as ground truth for evaluation and (when applicable) supervision for learning the merge scorer, while the clustering pipeline itself operates without labels at test time.

For the synthetic benchmarks, K corresponds to the number of geometric groups defined by the dataset construction and is treated as the ground-truth clustering. For

the real datasets, K corresponds to the number of semantic classes described above. Across all datasets, labels are used only for training the pairwise merge scorer (when applicable) and for evaluation; clustering decisions at inference follow the learned merge scores described in Section 3. This separation ensures that the reported performance reflects the behavior of the learned merge policy and the micro-cluster merging procedure, rather than relying on label information at test time.

4.2 Protocol and evaluation metrics

All runs follow a fixed protocol to ensure comparability across methods. We set the random seed to 42 and split each dataset into 80% training and 20% testing using the density-balanced strategy described in Section 3. For GOTHIC, the merge-scoring module is fitted using only the training split, and all reported results are computed on the corresponding split (training or testing). Although many classical clustering baselines (e.g., k-means, spectral clustering, and density-based methods) do not require a train/test split in their original formulation, we adopt the same split for all methods to avoid any potential information leakage when learnable components are present (e.g., neural baselines and other parameterized procedures) and to evaluate every approach under an identical data-access constraint. Concretely, each method is run using only the training split to produce cluster assignments, and test metrics are computed by assigning test points using the method’s standard out-of-sample rule when applicable (for instance, nearest-centroid assignment for centroid-based models). This unified protocol yields a controlled comparison that isolates differences in clustering principles rather than differences in how much data each method effectively uses.

- **External metrics (agreement with ground truth).** We report NMI as a normalized mutual-information measure of partition agreement, AMI as its chance-corrected variant [76], ARI as a chance-corrected pairwise agreement score [39], FMI as a precision/recall-style pairwise similarity between partitions [28], and ACC computed after the best one-to-one mapping between predicted cluster IDs and ground-truth labels (bipartite matching).
- **Internal metrics (structure in feature space).** We report the Silhouette coefficient to compare within-cluster cohesion against separation from the nearest competing cluster [59], the Davies–Bouldin index to summarize cluster scatter relative to inter-cluster distances [19], and the Calinski–Harabasz score to compare between-cluster dispersion to within-cluster dispersion [10].

Experimental settings. We evaluate GOTHIC against a mix of traditional and modern clustering baselines under a unified protocol. Traditional baselines include centroid-based partitioning (k-means [47, 50]), spectral graph partitioning (Spectral Clustering [53]), and density-based clustering (DBSCAN [25] and its hierarchical extension HDBSCAN [11]). We also include a density-peak style method (INS-DPC [46]) that follows the decision principle of Density Peaks Clustering [57], as well as adaptive and multi-density DBSCAN variants (AMD-DBSCAN, MDBSCAN) built on the core DBSCAN mechanism [25]. Modern baselines include deep clustering (IDEC [35] built on DEC-style objectives [79]) and graph neural approaches (GNN

and a contrastive GNN variant) that rely on GCN-style message passing [45] and contrastive/self-supervised principles used in graph representation learning [75, 85].

Table 2 reports the shared GOTHIC architecture and optimization settings, Table 3 lists dataset-dependent GOTHIC hyperparameters, and Table 4 summarizes baseline hyperparameters. For methods that require a target number of clusters, we use the dataset-specific value k_{target} shown in Table 3.

For `olivetti_faces`, we apply PCA to 128 dimensions only for GOTHIC before micro-clustering and graph construction. This preprocessing improves the reliability of distance-based neighborhood graphs in very high dimensions (here $d = 4096$) and reduces the cost of centroid and edge-distance computations, while preserving the dominant variance structure of the data [1].

These metrics and settings are used in the following subsections to summarize performance across datasets and to compare GOTHIC with baselines under the same protocol.

Setting	Value
Model dimension d	32
Attention heads	4
MLP hidden size	64
Boundary parameter b	5
Training epochs	2000
Learning rate	10^{-3}
Weight decay	10^{-4}

Table 2: Shared GOTHIC architecture and optimization hyperparameters (used for majority of datasets).

Table 3 lists dataset-specific settings controlling the micro-cluster budget (n_{micro}), graph sparsity via the distance quantile (q), and the depth of contextualization in the merge scorer (L).

Table 4 reports the primary hyperparameters for each baseline. These settings are kept fixed across datasets to emphasize differences between clustering principles rather than per-dataset retuning.

4.3 Quantitative results on synthetic and real datasets

We report quantitative clustering performance under the protocol in Subsection 4.2. For each dataset, models are fit on the training split and evaluated on the held-out test split. We report NMI, AMI, ARI, FMI, and clustering accuracy (ACC), where higher values indicate better agreement with the ground-truth partition.

Dataset	k_{target}	n_{micro}	q	L
compound	6	91	0.3	2
aggregation	7	120	0.3	2
d31	31	85	0.3	2
flame	2	25	0.3	2
jain	2	50	0.3	2
noisy_circles	2	100	0.3	2
pathbased	3	80	0.15	3
r15	15	45	0.3	2
wine	3	5	0.6	3
iris	3	70	0.3	2
breast_cancer	2	15	0.9	1
digits	10	120	0.4	4
olivetti_faces	40	120	0.4	4

Table 3: Dataset-dependent GOTHIC hyperparameters. Here n_{micro} is the micro-node budget, q is the distance quantile, and L is the number of transformer layers. For olivetti_faces, PCA(128) is applied before running GOTHIC.

Method	Hyperparameters (shared across datasets)
k-means	$n_{\text{init}} = 50$, $\text{max_iter} = 500$.
Spectral Clustering	$k = k_{\text{target}}$ (default implementation settings).
DBSCAN	$\epsilon = 0.2$, $\text{min_samples} = 5$.
HDBSCAN	$\text{min_cluster_size} = 5$, $\text{min_samples} = 5$, selection method EOM, $\text{cluster_selection_epsilon} = 0$.
INSDPC	$k_{\text{neighbors}} = 30$.
AMD-DBSCAN	$\epsilon = 1.0$, $\text{min_samples} = 5$, $k_{\text{scale}} = 15$.
MDBSCAN	$\epsilon_{\text{min}} = 0.05$, $\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 1.0$, $n_{\text{levels}} = 10$, $\text{min_samples} = 5$.
GNN	$\text{knn}_k = 10$, $\text{hidden} = 64$, $\text{embed} = 16$, $\text{dropout} = 0.1$, $\text{lr} = 10^{-2}$, $\text{weight decay} = 10^{-4}$, $\text{epochs} = 200$.
Contrastive GNN	$\text{knn}_k = 10$, $\text{hidden} = 128$, $\text{embed} = 64$, $\text{dropout} = 0.1$, $\text{epochs} = 300$, $\text{lr} = 10^{-3}$, $\text{weight decay} = 10^{-4}$, $\text{temperature} = 0.2$, $\text{edge_drop} = 0.2$, $\text{feat_drop} = 0.2$.
IDEC	$\text{latent} = 16$, $\text{hidden} = 128$, $\text{pretrain epochs} = 100$, $\text{finetune epochs} = 200$, $\text{lr} = 10^{-3}$, $\alpha = 1.0$, $\gamma = 1.0$, $\text{update_interval} = 10$.

Table 4: Baseline hyperparameters used in the evaluations.

Synthetic benchmarks. Tables 5 and 6 summarize test-split results on synthetic datasets constructed to stress different clustering regimes. The suite includes mixture-like layouts with varying separation, non-convex geometries, and connectivity-driven structures in which clusters are defined by paths or manifolds rather than compact blobs. These benchmarks therefore expose when centroid assumptions break down, when a single density scale is insufficient, and when correctly recovering global connectivity is essential for high agreement across all metrics.

Across the first four synthetic datasets (Table 5), GOTHIC recovers the ground-truth partition, reaching 1.00 on all metrics for compound, aggregation, d31, and flame. On compound, spectral clustering is the strongest baseline (NMI 0.86, ARI 0.81, ACC 0.86), followed by HDBSCAN (ARI 0.74). On aggregation, both GOTHIC and spectral clustering achieve perfect recovery, indicating that the dataset aligns well with graph-Laplacian structure. On d31 (k=31), several methods also reach the optimum (k-means, spectral, and IDEC), while single-scale density baselines such as DBSCAN and AMD-DBSCAN collapse to degenerate partitions. Finally, flame highlights a common metric mismatch: k-means obtains high ACC (0.98) but lower agreement scores (NMI/AMI 0.87/0.87), suggesting that label-permutation accuracy can remain high despite structural merge/split errors. In contrast, GOTHIC remains consistent across information-theoretic and pair-counting metrics.

The second synthetic block (Table 6) emphasizes non-spherical and connectivity-driven structure. On noisy_circles, centroid-based clustering fails completely, while density-based clustering partially recovers the ring (HDBSCAN NMI 0.63, ARI 0.70, ACC 0.82). GOTHIC achieves perfect recovery, indicating that it can preserve connectivity in non-convex geometries without requiring manual density-scale tuning. The pathbased dataset is particularly informative: baselines degrade substantially (HDBSCAN ARI 0.68; spectral ARI 0.52), while GOTHIC recovers the exact partition on the test split. On jain, HDBSCAN remains the strongest traditional baseline (ARI 0.94) but still falls short of full agreement. Finally, on r15, multiple methods reach the optimum (k-means, spectral, and IDEC), and GOTHIC matches this ceiling, showing that the proposed merging policy does not sacrifice easy cases to improve hard ones. Overall, the synthetic results highlight that GOTHIC remains robust across regimes, with the largest gains appearing when cluster geometry deviates from spherical prototypes or when a single density scale is insufficient.

Real-data benchmarks. Table 7 reports test-split clustering performance on five real datasets (wine, iris, breast_cancer, digits, and olivetti_faces) evaluated under the same protocol, data splits, and baseline hyperparameters. This suite spans low-dimensional tabular data and higher-dimensional settings with increased overlap and nuisance variation, providing a complementary view beyond controlled synthetic structure and testing robustness under realistic distributions preprocessing described earlier.

On real datasets (Table 7), GOTHIC is the top-performing method overall, achieving the best (or tied-best) results across the suite, with the most pronounced advantages on higher-dimensional or more ambiguous benchmarks. On iris, GOTHIC reaches perfect agreement across all reported metrics (tied with IDEC), whereas k-means remains below perfect in accuracy. On wine, GOTHIC achieves the strongest

overall agreement (NMI 0.86, ARI 0.78, ACC 0.94), outperforming both the contrastive GNN and k-means under the same fixed-hyperparameter protocol. On `breast_cancer`, GOTHIC shows a clear margin over traditional baselines, improving substantially over HDBSCAN and k-means in both accuracy and chance-corrected agreement. On `digits`, performance is near-perfect for GOTHIC (ACC 1.00 with agreement scores close to 1.00), exceeding centroid, density, and deep/graph baselines. Finally, on `olivetti_faces`, GOTHIC remains the strongest method after the PCA preprocessing (NMI 0.93, ACC 0.80); while k-means attains relatively high NMI, its accuracy is markedly lower, and density-based methods tend to over-fragment the partition. Overall, the gap between methods widens on the more challenging image-derived datasets, indicating that learned, graph-informed merging is especially beneficial when cluster boundaries are subtle and multi-scale.

Internal metrics. We also report label-free criteria computed directly from the predicted partition in feature space. Specifically, we compute the Silhouette coefficient (Sil), the Davies–Bouldin index (DB), and the Calinski–Harabasz score (CH). To keep the presentation compact while still covering diverse regimes, Table 8 reports these metrics on a set of representative datasets where the internal scores are well-defined.

Internal metrics provide a complementary, label-free view of clustering structure, but they primarily reflect geometric cohesion/separation in the embedding space. On `flame`, GOTHIC achieves the strongest values on all three criteria, indicating a partition that is simultaneously cohesive (high Sil), well-separated (low DB), and globally dispersed (high CH). On `aggregation`, GOTHIC attains the best Sil and DB, while kmeans yields the largest CH, suggesting that multiple solutions can appear favorable depending on whether the index emphasizes local compactness or global between-cluster dispersion.

The remaining datasets highlight typical trade-offs. On `r15`, several approaches produce highly compact partitions, with GOTHIC tying for the best Sil and remaining near-optimal on DB/CH. On `breast_cancer`, GOTHIC attains the highest CH, whereas kmeans/idec score better on Sil/DB, reflecting that optimizing Euclidean compactness is not always aligned with recovering class-consistent structure. On `olivetti_faces`, IDEC produces the best DB and CH, while GOTHIC yields the highest Sil; this gap illustrates that internal indices can prefer different cluster geometries in difficult high-dimensional settings. Overall, GOTHIC remains competitive under internal criteria on diverse regimes, with its strongest advantages appearing when coherent global structure is recovered without over-fragmentation.

Ablation Study. GOTHIC includes a small set of intuitive hyperparameters that control how the method represents structure before the final hierarchical merging. On the `wine` dataset, two of these controls dominate the observed behavior: the micro-cluster budget (n_{micro}), which determines the resolution of the initial over-clustering, and the distance quantile, which determines how densely the micro-cluster graph is connected. Figure 2 reports the resulting test ACC and test NMI while varying each parameter independently. In each sweep, the non-varied parameter is held fixed (the distance quantile is fixed while varying n_{micro} , and n_{micro} is fixed while varying the distance quantile), and all remaining settings follow the same experimental configuration used for `wine` in the main evaluation. Because `wine` is relatively small and

low-dimensional, the curves provide a clear view of how structural choices in the micro-graph translate into clustering quality, without being confounded by high-dimensional effects.

The micro-cluster budget controls a direct trade-off between representational detail and stability. When n_{micro} is too small, each micro-cluster contains many heterogeneous samples. This forces the pipeline to compress different local neighborhoods into the same node, removing boundary information that should remain separated until later merges. In this regime, the subsequent merging stage has fewer reliable cues, and both ACC and NMI remain below their best attainable values. As n_{micro} increases, micro-clusters become more homogeneous and better aligned with local geometry. This improves the quality of micro-node features, increases neighborhood purity, and produces a graph whose connected components and short paths better reflect the underlying class structure. Consequently, the metrics increase sharply and reach a strong operating region.

Increasing n_{micro} beyond a moderate range can reverse this benefit. Overly aggressive over-clustering fragments the data into many small micro-nodes, which makes boundary statistics noisier (fewer samples per node) and increases the number of candidate edges and merges. This amplifies the effect of small local inconsistencies that can propagate through hierarchical merging, producing avoidable splits or incorrect merges and lowering external agreement. The curve in Figure 2(a) therefore supports an intermediate regime for n_{micro} , where the representation is detailed enough to preserve neighborhood structure while remaining stable enough for consistent merging.

The distance quantile controls graph connectivity and therefore determines how much global evidence is available during merging. If the quantile is too low, the micro-graph is under-connected: micro-nodes belonging to the same true cluster may not be linked by edges, preventing the method from accumulating evidence across the cluster. In this regime, merging decisions are constrained by missing adjacency and the algorithm tends to produce fragmented components or incomplete merges, which is reflected by weaker ACC and NMI. As the quantile increases, the graph transitions into a well-connected regime where within-cluster connectivity is reliably captured. This enables the merge policy to observe consistent local-to-global cues across the micro-graph, producing rapid gains in both metrics.

After this transition, the curves stabilize, indicating diminishing returns from adding further edges on wine. Once the graph already encodes the essential adjacency patterns, additional edges mostly provide redundancy rather than new structural information. At the same time, excessively permissive connectivity can increase the number of cross-cluster edges, which may introduce misleading merge candidates in more challenging regimes. The observed plateau suggests that on wine the method quickly reaches a connectivity level sufficient for correct global merging and then remains robust across a range of higher quantiles. Overall, Figure 2(b) confirms that the distance quantile primarily acts as a sparsity/coverage knob: it must be large enough to avoid under-connecting true components, while overly dense graphs offer limited additional benefit on this dataset.

Finally, ACC and NMI do not necessarily move in lockstep because they capture different notions of agreement. ACC (after optimal label mapping) is pointwise and

Fig. 2: Ablation Study on wine for two key hyperparameters. Left: varying the micro-cluster budget reveals an intermediate regime that best balances representational detail and stability. Right: varying the distance quantile shows the transition from an under-connected micro-graph to a well-connected regime where performance stabilizes.

penalizes boundary swaps directly, while NMI is information-based and can remain comparatively stable when the overall grouping structure is preserved. On a small dataset such as wine, small changes affecting only a few borderline samples can therefore produce visible differences between the ACC and NMI trends, particularly in the over-fragmented regime of large n_{micro} .

4.4 Qualitative analysis on representative datasets

Quantitative metrics provide a concise summary of clustering performance, but they do not fully capture *how* and *why* different methods succeed or fail. To complement the numerical evaluation, we include qualitative visualizations that illustrate cluster structure, decision boundaries, and error patterns produced by GOTHIC and representative baselines. These visual analyses help reveal the geometric and topological properties underlying the reported scores and provide intuition for the observed performance differences.

Figure 3 provides a qualitative comparison on the Iris dataset under the same experimental protocol used throughout Section 4.3. The figure shows the ground-truth labeling together with the train/test split for the same random seed and density-balanced strategy. The top row corresponds to GOTHIC, while the bottom row corresponds to k-means. For visualization purposes, only the first two features of the Iris dataset are shown, although clustering is performed in the full $d = 4$ feature space.

Although Iris is relatively low-dimensional and well-structured, the figure reveals a subtle but meaningful difference between methods. In the k-means result, two test samples are misclustered. Examining the ground truth shows that these points lie close to the competing cluster boundary in the 2D projection, making them visually ambiguous. GOTHIC correctly assigns these samples, despite operating on the same split and without access to labels at test time. This qualitative behavior is consistent with the quantitative results in Table 7, where GOTHIC achieves perfect agreement across all reported metrics on Iris, while centroid-based and density-based baselines

Fig. 3: Qualitative visualization on the Iris dataset. Top row: GOTHIC. Bottom row: k-means. Each row shows the ground-truth labels and the corresponding train/test split under the shared experimental protocol. Only the first two features are shown for visualization clarity.

fall short. The improvement reflects GOTHIC’s ability to integrate local neighborhood evidence with global merge decisions, rather than relying solely on centroid proximity in the original feature space.

Figure 4 provides an analogous qualitative comparison on the *digits* dataset, contrasting GOTHIC with IDEC. Compared to Iris, digits is higher-dimensional and exhibits stronger class overlap, where visually similar categories (e.g., neighboring digit shapes) can induce boundary ambiguity in a 2D projection. For visualization purposes, only the first two features of the digits dataset are shown, although clustering is performed in the full feature space. IDEC yields several boundary swaps on ambiguous test samples, reflecting the difficulty of separating overlapping digit classes even with learned embeddings. In contrast, GOTHIC produces partitions that better preserve global connectivity through its micro-cluster graph and hierarchical merge policy, reducing confusions between nearby digit manifolds. This qualitative behavior aligns with the corresponding quantitative trends reported for digits in Table 7.

Figure 5 and Figure 6 provide compact visual summaries of the quantitative results reported in Tables 5, 6, and 7. Figure 5 visualizes clustering accuracy (ACC) for each dataset–method pair, while Figure 6 reports the mean performance of each method averaged across all datasets for each external metric (NMI, FMI, ARI, AMI, ACC). Both plots are derived directly from the table values and are included to make cross-dataset trends easier to inspect.

Fig. 4: Qualitative visualization on the digits dataset. Top row: GOTHC. Bottom row: IDEC. Each row shows the ground-truth labels and the corresponding train/test split under the shared experimental protocol. Only the first two features are shown for visualization clarity.

Two trends are immediately visible. First, GOTHC remains consistently strong across datasets, and its advantage is most pronounced on non-convex and connectivity-driven benchmarks (e.g., *noisy_circles* and *pathbased*), where centroid-based assumptions and a single density scale are unreliable. Second, baseline behavior is substantially less stable across datasets: DBSCAN collapses on several benchmarks, while HDBSCAN and INSDPC are competitive on specific regimes but exhibit larger performance variation, reflecting sensitivity to density scale selection, neighborhood choices, and fragmentation/merge errors.

These patterns also suggest a practical generalization beyond the specific benchmarks used here. When cluster identity depends on global connectivity (manifolds, rings, elongated paths) or when local density varies across regions, methods that rely primarily on centroid proximity or a fixed density threshold tend to produce systematic structural mistakes (splits, merges, or boundary swaps). In contrast, GOTHC’s micro-cluster graph representation and learned merge policy integrate local neighborhood evidence with global hierarchical consistency, making the resulting partitions more robust to geometric nonlinearity, multi-scale structure, and borderline samples. This qualitative summary matches the dataset-level results in Tables 5, 6, and 7, and provides intuition for why the gains are strongest in complex-geometry regimes.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 provide a qualitative overview of the synthetic benchmarks using a paired visualization strategy. For each dataset, we show the ground-truth partition (GT) alongside the corresponding GOTHC micro-cluster graph produced under the shared experimental protocol (Section 4.2). Since these datasets are inherently two-dimensional, the plots directly reflect the geometric and topological structure that

Fig. 5: Heatmap visualization of clustering accuracy (ACC) across all datasets and methods, computed from Tables 5, 6, and 7.

Fig. 6: Mean external metrics (NMI, FMI, ARI, AMI, ACC) for each method averaged across all datasets, computed from Tables 5, 6, and 7.

drives clustering difficulty. This paired layout makes it easy to visually verify when a representation preserves global connectivity (e.g., rings or elongated paths), when it risks erroneous merges between nearby components, and when it over-fragments a single cluster under local density variation. The qualitative patterns are consistent with the quantitative results in Tables 5 and 6, where the largest gains are observed on non-convex and connectivity-driven regimes (e.g., *noisy_circles* and *pathbased*), while more mixture-like cases (e.g., *r15*) allow multiple methods to perform well.

compound (micro) aggregation (micro) d31 (micro) flame (micro)
Fig. 7: Synthetic datasets (part I): ground-truth partitions (top row) and corresponding GOthic micro-cluster graphs (bottom row) for *compound*, *aggregation*, *d31*, and *flame*.

jain (micro) noisy_circles (micro) pathbased (micro) r15 (micro)
Fig. 8: Synthetic datasets (part II): ground-truth partitions (top row) and corresponding GOthic micro-cluster graphs (bottom row) for *jain*, *noisy_circles*, *pathbased*, and *r15*.

Across the synthetic suite, the micro-cluster graphs provide intuition for GOthic’s stability across regimes. In connectivity-driven datasets such as *noisy_circles* and *pathbased* (Figure 8), the micro-graphs preserve long-range adjacency that defines cluster identity beyond centroid proximity, consistent with the strong agreement scores in Table 6. In multi-cluster and fine-grained cases such as *d31* (Figure 7), the micro-graph forms compact components aligned with the true partition, enabling correct merges without collapsing nearby clusters. In mixture-like layouts such as *r15* (Figure 8), the structure is already well-separated, explaining

why multiple baselines can perform strongly; importantly, GOTHIC does not sacrifice these easy cases while improving harder regimes. Overall, the paired visualizations support the conclusion drawn from Tables 5 and 6: the largest gains arise when global connectivity and multi-scale structure matter, because the micro-graph representation provides a more faithful substrate for hierarchical merging than either centroid proximity or a single density threshold.

Figure 9 provides an analogous qualitative summary for the real datasets. Since these datasets are not inherently two-dimensional, the plots are shown in a fixed 2D view for inspection, while all quantitative results are computed in the original feature space (Table 7). The paired view contrasts ground-truth class structure with the learned micro-cluster graph, highlighting where class overlap and boundary ambiguity can drive systematic errors for centroid-based methods.

Fig. 9: Real datasets: ground-truth partitions (top row) and corresponding GOTHIC micro-cluster graphs (bottom row) for *iris* and *breast_cancer*. Visualizations are shown in a fixed 2D view for inspection, while clustering results are computed in the original feature space (Table 7).

On *iris*, the micro-graph forms clean, well-separated components (Figure 9), matching the perfect agreement across all external metrics reported in Table 7. On *breast_cancer*, the visualization reveals stronger overlap and gradual transitions between classes, where centroid-based clustering is prone to systematic misassignment. By deferring final decisions to a learned merge policy operating on the micro-graph, GOTHIC can reconcile local ambiguity with global consistency, explaining its advantage on this dataset in Table 7. These observations generalize to higher-dimensional and noisier settings: when class boundaries are not well described by a single centroid

or when local density varies across regions, explicitly modeling micro-level structure and connectivity provides a more reliable basis for robust hierarchical clustering.

Limitations. Despite its strong empirical performance, GOTHIC has several limitations that merit discussion. First, the use of a transformer-based merge scorer introduces additional computational cost during training compared to purely geometric or density-based clustering methods. Although inference remains lightweight once the micro-cluster graph is constructed, training the scorer requires sufficient data coverage to learn meaningful merge decisions, and performance may degrade when the training split is not representative of the test distribution. This sensitivity is inherent to data-driven attention mechanisms, which rely on exposure to diverse structural patterns in order to generalize reliably.

Second, GOTHIC introduces multiple architectural and algorithmic hyperparameters, including the micro-node budget, graph construction thresholds, transformer depth, and attention dimensionality. While these parameters were fixed or selected using simple heuristics in our experiments, suboptimal configurations may affect performance on new datasets, particularly in regimes with extreme imbalance, high dimensionality, or limited sample size. More broadly, as with many hybrid learning-based clustering methods, the interaction between representation learning and graph structure adds complexity to model selection and interpretability.

Several strategies can mitigate these limitations. Automated hyperparameter optimization or multi-fidelity search could reduce sensitivity to manual tuning while keeping computational cost manageable. In addition, dataset similarity measures—based on distributional statistics, intrinsic dimensionality, or graph structural descriptors—could be used to identify previously seen datasets with comparable structure, enabling transfer of suitable hyperparameter settings or initialization schemes. More generally, lightweight pretraining of the merge scorer on a diverse library of synthetic or real datasets may improve robustness and reduce the need for extensive retraining when adapting to new domains.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This paper introduced **GOTHIC**, a graph-overclustered hierarchical clustering framework that couples a micro-cluster graph representation with a transformer-based merge scorer to address regimes where centroid assumptions and single-scale density thresholds break down. By first over-clustering into locally coherent micro-nodes and then learning merge decisions in a context-aware manner over the induced graph, GOTHIC can preserve non-convex boundaries, encode long-range connectivity cues, and remain robust under heterogeneous density without using labels at test time. Under a fixed and reproducible protocol with a density-balanced train/test split, GOTHIC achieved strong and consistent performance across both synthetic SIPU benchmarks and real datasets spanning low-dimensional tabular data and higher-dimensional image-derived features; its largest gains appeared on connectivity-driven and multi-scale geometries where classical baselines are prone to fragmentation or incorrect merges, while still matching ceiling performance on easier mixture-like cases. Complementary internal indices and qualitative visualizations further supported these

findings by illustrating cohesive partitions and reduced boundary confusions relative to representative baselines, and the ablation study clarified how the micro-cluster budget and graph connectivity act as dominant structural controls, favoring an intermediate micro-resolution and sufficient graph coverage. Several directions can further strengthen GOTHIC. Reducing computational cost remains important, and can be pursued through parameter-efficient attention variants, structured pruning, and faster or sparser graph construction by approximate neighbor search and edge candidate screening to improve scalability on larger datasets. Robustness can be improved by reducing sensitivity to dataset-specific hyperparameters, including more principled selection rules for the micro-cluster budget and connectivity thresholds, and by extending the framework toward estimating the number of clusters rather than relying on a target value when required. Generalization across domains is another key direction when pretraining the merge scorer on diverse synthetic structures and transferring to new datasets using dataset-similarity signals or graph-structural descriptors could reduce retraining needs and stabilize performance. Finally, streaming and incremental extensions that update the micro-graph and merge decisions as new samples arrive, together with broader evaluation on higher-dimensional, noisier, mixed-type, and domain-specific datasets, would provide a more comprehensive assessment of robustness and help delineate when learned, graph-informed merging yields the greatest practical benefit.

Dataset	Model	NMI	FMI	ARI	AMI	ACC
compound	gothic	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	kmeans	0.77	0.68	0.59	0.74	0.74
	spectral	0.86	0.86	0.81	0.84	0.86
	dbscan	0.00	0.49	0.00	0.00	0.40
	hdbscan	0.80	0.83	0.74	0.79	0.75
	insdpc	0.78	0.65	0.55	0.75	0.68
	amd_dbscan	0.00	0.49	0.00	0.00	0.40
	mdbscan	0.55	0.51	0.26	0.50	0.54
	gnn	0.66	0.69	0.58	0.62	0.78
	gnn_contrastive	0.77	0.79	0.72	0.74	0.81
idec	0.80	0.69	0.60	0.78	0.72	
aggregation	gothic	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	kmeans	0.92	0.83	0.79	0.91	0.78
	spectral	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	dbscan	0.00	0.46	0.00	0.00	0.35
	hdbscan	0.89	0.86	0.81	0.88	0.83
	insdpc	0.84	0.72	0.65	0.82	0.73
	amd_dbscan	0.89	0.86	0.81	0.88	0.83
	mdbscan	0.62	0.55	0.42	0.54	0.57
	gnn	0.68	0.55	0.43	0.65	0.61
	gnn_contrastive	0.76	0.63	0.54	0.74	0.67
idec	0.89	0.83	0.78	0.88	0.88	
d31	gothic	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	kmeans	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	spectral	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	dbscan	0.02	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.04
	hdbscan	0.84	0.49	0.36	0.81	0.53
	insdpc	1.00	0.99	0.99	1.00	1.00
	amd_dbscan	0.08	0.18	0.00	0.07	0.06
	mdbscan	0.87	0.59	0.50	0.85	0.55
	gnn	0.86	0.66	0.65	0.83	0.71
	gnn_contrastive	0.91	0.76	0.75	0.88	0.79
idec	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	
flame	gothic	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	kmeans	0.87	0.96	0.92	0.87	0.98
	spectral	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.65
	dbscan	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.65
	hdbscan	0.43	0.63	0.36	0.40	0.81
	insdpc	0.04	0.54	0.04	0.02	0.62
	amd_dbscan	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.65
	mdbscan	0.39	0.54	0.21	0.35	0.58
	gnn	0.18	0.58	-0.03	0.17	0.56
	gnn_contrastive	0.25	0.58	0.06	0.24	0.65
idec	0.60	0.81	0.62	0.60	0.90	

Table 5: Synthetic datasets: test-split clustering performance on compound, aggregation, d31, and flame, reported using NMI, FMI, ARI, AMI, and ACC.

Dataset	Model	NMI	FMI	ARI	AMI	ACC
jain	gothic	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	kmeans	0.39	0.69	0.31	0.38	0.78
	spectral	0.24	0.80	0.25	0.23	0.81
	dbscan	0.00	0.78	0.00	0.00	0.74
	hdbscan	0.88	0.98	0.94	0.87	0.82
	insdpc	0.09	0.65	-0.10	0.08	0.61
	amd_dbscan	0.00	0.78	0.00	0.00	0.74
	mdbscan	0.16	0.41	-0.12	0.09	0.36
	gnn	0.46	0.76	0.45	0.46	0.84
	gnn_contrastive	0.46	0.76	0.45	0.46	0.84
idec	0.29	0.61	0.13	0.28	0.69	
noisy_circles	gothic	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	kmeans	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.53
	spectral	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.52
	dbscan	0.00	0.71	0.00	0.00	0.50
	hdbscan	0.63	0.83	0.70	0.62	0.82
	insdpc	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.51
	amd_dbscan	0.00	0.71	0.00	0.00	0.50
	mdbscan	0.42	0.60	0.35	0.40	0.56
	gnn	0.00	0.53	0.00	0.00	0.54
	gnn_contrastive	0.01	0.50	0.01	0.00	0.55
idec	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.54	
pathbased	gothic	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	kmeans	0.49	0.64	0.39	0.47	0.65
	spectral	0.60	0.69	0.52	0.59	0.80
	dbscan	0.00	0.57	0.00	0.00	0.37
	hdbscan	0.71	0.78	0.68	0.69	0.68
	insdpc	0.50	0.64	0.39	0.49	0.63
	amd_dbscan	0.00	0.57	0.00	0.00	0.37
	mdbscan	0.03	0.56	0.00	0.00	0.37
	gnn	0.42	0.55	0.32	0.40	0.62
	gnn_contrastive	0.45	0.58	0.36	0.43	0.70
idec	0.49	0.64	0.39	0.47	0.65	
r15	gothic	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	kmeans	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	spectral	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	dbscan	0.60	0.25	0.10	0.41	0.48
	hdbscan	0.74	0.44	0.24	0.67	0.53
	insdpc	0.92	0.75	0.70	0.89	0.73
	amd_dbscan	0.74	0.44	0.24	0.67	0.53
	mdbscan	0.74	0.44	0.24	0.67	0.53
	gnn	0.78	0.57	0.52	0.70	0.59
	gnn_contrastive	0.78	0.57	0.52	0.70	0.59
idec	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	

Table 6: Synthetic datasets: test-split clustering performance on jain, noisy_circles, pathbased, and r15, reported using NMI, FMI, ARI, AMI, and ACC.

Dataset	Model	NMI	FMI	ARI	AMI	ACC
wine	gothic	0.86	0.85	0.78	0.81	0.94
	kmeans	0.76	0.72	0.52	0.66	0.89
	spectral	0.00	0.57	0.00	0.00	0.39
	dbscan	0.00	0.57	0.00	0.00	0.39
	hdbscan	0.63	0.53	0.36	0.56	0.44
	insdpc	0.79	0.80	0.71	0.77	0.89
	amd_dbscan	0.79	0.80	0.71	0.77	0.89
	mdbscan	0.00	0.57	0.00	0.00	0.39
	gnn	0.80	0.83	0.74	0.79	0.91
	gnn_contrastive	0.82	0.84	0.75	0.81	0.92
	idec	0.50	0.64	0.39	0.49	0.62
iris	gothic	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	kmeans	0.74	0.79	0.62	0.73	0.90
	spectral	0.00	0.56	0.00	0.00	0.33
	dbscan	0.00	0.56	0.00	0.00	0.33
	hdbscan	0.73	0.76	0.55	0.72	0.67
	insdpc	0.67	0.69	0.47	0.64	0.60
	amd_dbscan	0.67	0.69	0.47	0.64	0.60
	mdbscan	0.73	0.76	0.55	0.72	0.67
	gnn	0.70	0.75	0.54	0.69	0.93
	gnn_contrastive	0.51	0.69	0.36	0.49	0.85
	idec	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
breast_cancer	gothic	0.77	0.92	0.83	0.77	0.96
	kmeans	0.20	0.72	0.15	0.19	0.72
	spectral	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.63
	dbscan	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.63
	hdbscan	0.35	0.76	0.42	0.38	0.81
	insdpc	0.23	0.59	0.08	0.26	0.65
	amd_dbscan	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.63
	mdbscan	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.63
	gnn	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.63
	gnn_contrastive	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.63
	idec	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.63
digits	gothic	0.99	0.99	0.98	0.99	1.00
	kmeans	0.61	0.75	0.51	0.60	0.73
	spectral	0.00	0.47	0.00	0.00	0.10
	dbscan	0.00	0.47	0.00	0.00	0.10
	hdbscan	0.10	0.49	0.05	0.03	0.11
	insdpc	0.34	0.55	0.26	0.33	0.35
	amd_dbscan	0.00	0.47	0.00	0.00	0.10
	mdbscan	0.05	0.47	0.01	0.03	0.11
	gnn	0.81	0.89	0.81	0.81	0.91
	gnn_contrastive	0.91	0.94	0.90	0.91	0.93
	idec	0.88	0.73	0.65	0.83	0.82
olivetti_faces	gothic	0.93	0.54	0.46	0.72	0.80
	kmeans	0.86	0.44	0.29	0.61	0.61
	spectral	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.03
	dbscan	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.03
	hdbscan	0.46	0.25	0.11	0.34	0.53
	insdpc	0.14	0.11	0.02	0.09	0.12
	amd_dbscan	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.03
	mdbscan	0.15	0.13	0.02	0.08	0.18
	gnn	0.58	0.36	0.23	0.38	0.42
	gnn_contrastive	0.70	0.40	0.29	0.48	0.57
	idec	0.78	0.32	0.16	0.54	0.65

Table 7: Real datasets: test-split clustering performance of GOTHIC and all baselines under the shared evaluation protocol. Results are reported using NMI, FMI, ARI, AMI, and ACC.

Dataset	Model	Sil \uparrow	DB \downarrow	CH \uparrow
flame	gothic	0.698	0.384	122.44
	kmeans	0.656	0.456	97.38
	hdbscan	0.028	1.012	18.68
	insdpc	0.082	3.457	3.53
	idec	0.538	0.677	66.81
aggregation	gothic	0.650	0.401	432.64
	kmeans	0.573	0.665	461.57
	hdbscan	0.549	0.479	239.38
	insdpc	0.441	0.803	293.63
	idec	0.557	0.658	448.24
r15	gothic	0.924	0.112	7764.45
	kmeans	0.924	0.112	7764.45
	hdbscan	0.681	0.310	148.59
	insdpc	0.740	0.370	519.87
	idec	0.924	0.113	8036.13
breast_cancer	gothic	0.627	0.599	198.85
	kmeans	0.721	0.390	189.33
	hdbscan	0.279	0.902	65.82
	insdpc	0.192	0.785	42.26
	idec	0.704	0.381	138.39
olivetti_faces	gothic	0.299	1.239	5.39
	kmeans	0.156	1.294	5.09
	hdbscan	-0.078	2.974	2.10
	insdpc	0.095	1.395	4.44
	idec	0.192	0.716	87.51

Table 8: Internal metrics on real and synthetic datasets (test split). Sil denotes the Silhouette coefficient, DB the Davies–Bouldin index, and CH the Calinski–Harabasz score, computed from the predicted partition in feature space. Boldface marks the best value per dataset and metric among the reported methods.

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